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Twin to Twin Transfusion Syndrome in Monochorionic Monoamniotic Twins

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Abstract

Twin to twin transfusion syndrome is an infrequent complication in a monozygotic twin pregnancy. There exists a “donor” twin that donates blood to a “recipient” twin via deep artery to vein anastomosis. This sets up a “oligo-poly” sequence between the twins. The most prevalent treatment is aimed at ablation of the anastomosis. This is a case report of a 27 year old third gravida patient who presented at estimated gestational age of 20 weeks, with outside USG findings of MCMA twins with mild polyhydramnios in first twin and small sized echogenic of both kidneys in second twin. She was managed by medically terminating the pregnancy and delivering the abortuses. As TTTS is a rare complication, a systemic detailed ultrasound with Doppler should be carried out.

Keywords: Twin to Twin Transfusion Syndrome, Monochorionic, Monoamniotic Twins

Introduction

Multifetal pregnancy is a high risk pregnancy associated with maternal and fetal complications. The incidence of multifetal pregnancy has increased owing to artificial reproductive techniques and advancing maternal age. The current rate of multifetal pregnancy is 33.3 per 1000 births (2017) according to US national statistics. ¹ Earlier, Hellin’s rule was postulated as a rough estimate of the incidence of twinning. The maternal complications in a multifetal gestation are preterm labour, preterm delivery, low birth weight baby, anemia, hyperemesis, hypertension (predisposing to pre-eclampsia, placental abruption and HELLP syndrome), polyhydramnios and post-partum haemorrhage. Fetal complications can be spontaneous abortion, vanishing twin and structural anomalies like, acardiac twin due to TRAP sequence and twin to twin transfusion syndrome. The incidence of TTTS is 10-15% in MCDA pregnancies and 5-10% in MCMA pregnancies. In the pathophysiology of TTTS, there is blood flow from one twin to the other through abnormal deep arteriovenous anastomosis over the chorionic surface of placenta. This results in hypervolemia in recipient twin and oligohydramnios in the donor twin. TTTS is associated with poor fetal outcome and can also lead to fatality.

Case report

A booked case of a 27-year-old third gravida patient with 1 live female child of seven years and history of 1 spontaneous abortion presented to SCL Hospital at five months of amenorrhea. She is a home maker with primary education. She came with her outside USG of 17-19 week maturity was suggestive of MCMA twins with mild polyhydramnios with first fetus showing over distended bladder and the other showing small sized echogenicity of both kidneys. She had no complaints at presentation. She had no significant medical or surgical

history and the pregnancy was conceived spontaneously. She was conscious, cooperative and oriented, did not demonstrate pallor or edema and was vitally stable. Her per abdominal findings suggested the fundal height to be around 32 weeks of gestation (symphysiofundal height 32 cm) and fetal parts were difficult to palpate. Her repeat scan at SCL Hospital revealed intrauterine twin gestation with first twin with variable presentation, 20 weeks of maturity, 330 gm of estimated fetal weight and single vertical pocket of 13.76 cm. It also demonstrated pericardial effusion, gross cardiomegaly and gross tricuspid regurgitation suggestive of CHD (Ebstein anomaly). The umbilical artery Doppler was normal. Fetus 2 also had a variable presentation. The estimated fetal weight and age was 178 gm and 17 weeks respectively. There was evidence of a IV septal defect measuring approximately 5.1 mm. The right ventricle appeared hypoplastic with narrow pulmonary artery calibre. Both kidneys appeared echogenic. Liquor could not be detected. A single placenta with two umbilical cords confirmed monochorionicity. Medical termination of pregnancy was carried out and both abortuses were delivered on 4/9/24. Abortus 1 weighed 285 gm and was substantially more developed in comparison the second abortus which weighed 150 gm. Post partum findings of the patient were normal. She was hemodynamically stable and was discharged on antibiotics and hematinics on the fourth post partum day. She had no complaints when she presented in the OPD after four weeks.

Figure 1- gross polyhydramnios

Figure 2- tricuspid regurgitation

Figure 3- cardiomegaly and pericardial effusion in recipient twin

Figure 4- both abortuses demonstrating significant growth discordance

Discussion

This is a case report of Twin to Twin Transfusion Syndrome in a monochorionic monoamniotic twin pregnancy necessitating medical termination. TTTS results due to

unidirectional blood flow through deep arteriovenous anastomosis over chorionic surface of placenta. These anastomosis lead to draining of arterial blood of one twin the venous system of the other twin. This imbalance of blood flow results in TTTS. There also exist vein to vein and artery to artery anastomosis on the superficial aspect which are bidirectional. Hence, research suggests artery to artery anastomoses to be protective against TTTS. TTTS can be seen in 10-15% MCDA pregnancies and in 5-10% of MCMA pregnancies. Severe TTTS can be seen in 1% of monochorionic pregnancies.²

TTTS usually presents in the second trimester. It can cause premature rupture of membranes, preterm labour, mortality due to heart failure in either fetus. Untreated TTTS leads to fetal demise in upto 90% of cases and morbidity rates of over 50% in survivors.³

The donor twin in TTTS develops anemia, growth restriction, oligohydramnios and eventually renal failure. Whereas, recipient twin develops polycythemia, polyhydramnios, and over time develops heart failure owing to circulatory overload and hypertrophic cardiomyopathy. This may manifest as hydrops. Furthermore, polycythemia may also lead to hyperbilirubinemia and kernicterus. Abnormal arterial circulation can lead to ischemic necrosis and intestinal perforation and brain damage. The neurological manifestations exhibited are cerebral palsy, microcephaly, porencephaly and multicystic encephalomalacia.

Prediction⁴

TTTS can be predicted at 11-14 weeks by 3 markers:

1. Discrepancy in CRL between both fetuses. This has a low sensitivity of about 8.3%.
2. Intertwin difference in nuchal translucency of ≥ 0.6 mm has sensitivity of 50% and specificity of 92%.
3. Abnormal ductus venosus blood flow in at least as the only marker demonstrates 15 times more risk of TTTS.

In a pregnancy with discrepant nuchal translucency (≥ 0.6 mm) with abnormal ductus venosus blood flow in at least 1 fetus, the risk of development of TTTS was 21 times higher.

Diagnosis

TTTS in monochorionic twins can be diagnosed by serial sonography at two weeks' interval 16 week of gestation onwards. On an ultrasound, fetal biometry, amniotic fluid (oligohydramnios and polyhydramnios are usually defined as SVP < 2 cm and > 8 cm respectively), Doppler changes in umbilical artery, umbilical vein and ductus venosus, bladder examination and MCA PSV for TAPS should be carried out.

Quintero staging⁵

- Stage I- Oligo- poly sequence + donor bladder visible
- Stage II- Oligo- poly sequence + donor bladder not visible
- Stage III- Abnormal Doppler findings
 - Donor twin- AEDF/ REDF in umbilical artery
 - Recipient twin- Abnormal flow in ductus venosus or pulsatile umbilical vein.
- Stage IV- Hydrops in one or both twins.
- Stage V- Death of one or both twins.

The Quintero staging is limited by atypical presentations where bladder of the donor is visible but is associated with abnormal Doppler changes. While higher stages are typically linked to a poorer perinatal prognosis, the clinical course of a specific case does not always follow a predictable progression. For instance, a stage I case might quickly advance to stage III within a few days, but regression can occur in up to 15 percent of stage I cases and 60 percent of stage II cases.⁶

The other staging systems use fetal echo to predict progress and severity of TTTS. They include-

1. CVPS staging- Parameters included are heart size, cardiac function, Doppler blood flow studies of umbilical artery, umbilical vein & ductus venosus.⁷

2. CHOP score- echo & peripheral Doppler findings.⁸
3. Cincinnati modification- atrioventricular valvular incompetence, ventricular wall thickening, ventricular function assessed by myocardial perfusion index.⁹

Management

Stage 1 of TTTS may remain stable or even reverse without intervention. The perinatal survival is around 86%. The prognosis of further stages is worse, leading to 70-100% perinatal loss.¹⁰

Broadly, there are 4 methods of managing TTTS.

1. Fetoscopic laser ablation- the Solomon technique, of artery to vein using Nd:YAG laser. This is considered the best management for stages II, III and IV TTTS in pregnancies <26 weeks. Non selective ablation of anastomoses has led to reverse TTTS, amniotic bands and limb necrosis. Hence, selective laser ablation is the preferred approach. Although stage I can be managed conservatively, signs like worsening polyhydramnios, shortening of cervical length and maternal discomfort indicate the need for fetoscopic laser treatment. The complication of laser ablation is that it may sometimes leave behind small incompletely coagulated anastomoses that could lead to TAPS (twin anemia polycythemia sequence).
 2. Amnioreduction- serial amnioreduction can be carried out to treat the polyhydramnios after 26 weeks.¹¹ It has shown to reduce the risk of preterm labour and also improves the uterine arterial flow. It is indicated when the AFI > 40 cm or SVP > 12 cm. Limitation of amnioreduction is that it requires multiple sittings compared to laser ablation which is a onetime procedure.
 3. Septostomy- this procedure involves making an opening in the intervening membrane using a 20-22 G needle. This facilitates the restoration of amniotic fluid volume to normalcy in both sacs.
 4. Fetal reduction can be considered before 20 weeks if there is presence of severe amniotic fluid changes. The aim is to occlude umbilical vein or umbilical cord.
- Monochorionic pregnancies complicated and treated for TTTS should be terminated between 34 to 36 + 6 weeks of gestation.¹²

Conclusion

TTTS is not an uncommon complication in multifetal gestation but is associated with a high risk of morbidity and mortality. Serial ultrasound scans, fetal echo and Doppler assessments with timely interventions can significantly improve the management of TTTS.

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